

A Comprehensive Review of the Utilization of Copper Slag as a Partial Replacement for Sand in Cement Concrete: Environmental and Engineering Implications

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Abstract

This Study focuses on the Properties of copper slag, as a partial replacement of sand for use in cement concrete. The use of copper slag in cement concrete provides potential environmental as well as economic benefits for all related industries, particularly in areas where a considerable amount of copper slag is produced. This paper reviews the Properties of copper slag and its effects on the engineering properties of cement, mortars and concrete. In this work, the concrete grade M40 selected and IS method is used for mix design. The various strength of concrete like Compressive, flexural and split tensile test for various replacements of fine aggregate using copper slag that are 0%, 15%, 30%, 45%, 60%, 75%, 90% and 100%. All specimens cured for 7, 28 days. By using the copper slag in construction field, the chance of getting pollution due to copper slag will be reduced and it will be the cost effective method for any construction industry. Certain previous investigations by different researchers were referred and with certain degree of variability the same is incorporated into the present study.

Keywords- Copper slag, compression strength, flexural Strength, split tensile

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1506

1. Introduction

Copper slag is an industrial waste material generated from the process of producing copper. It is estimated that about 1000 tons of copper slag are produced per day along with the conventional copper products (Hemalatha et al., 2022). Copper slag has been used for various purposes, such as sand blasting, abrasive tools, road construction, etc. (Laskar et al., 2022). However, a large amount of copper slag remains unused and poses environmental and health hazards. Table 1 shows major copper industries in India.

Table 1. Copper Industries in India

Company	Location	Industry	Key Products	Annual Turnover (in INR Crores)
Hindalco Industries Limited	Mumbai, Maharashtra	Copper Manufacturing	Copper cathodes, copper rods, copper alloys	Approximately 65,000 Crores (FY 2021-22)
Sterlite Copper	Thoothukudi, Tamil Nadu	Copper Manufacturing	Copper cathodes, copper wire rods, sulfuric acid	Approximately 10,000 Crores (FY 2021-22)
Birla Copper	Dahej, Gujarat	Copper Manufacturing	Copper cathodes, continuous cast copper rods	Approximately 3,000 Crores (FY 2021-22)
Aditya Birla Chemicals	Renukoot, Uttar Pradesh	Copper Manufacturing	Copper cathodes, copper sulfate, sulfuric acid	Approximately 2,500 Crores (FY 2021-22)

1507

Therefore, there is a need to find new ways to utilize copper slag in an eco-friendly and economical manner. One of the possible applications of copper slag is in the concrete industry as a replacement for fine aggregate. Fig 1. Shows composition of copper slag. It contains 20 % silica, hence suitable for partial replacement of fine aggregates in concrete.

Fig 1. Composition of Copper Slag

Fine aggregate is one of the main ingredients of concrete, which occupies 70-80% of the volume of concrete (Hemalatha et al., 2022). In India, there is a great demand for fine aggregate from civil engineering industry for road and concrete constructions. However, the availability of fine aggregate is limited and affected by natural factors, such as floods and rainy seasons (Tripathi et al., 2022).

Moreover, the extraction of fine aggregate from river sand causes environmental problems, such as erosion and depletion of natural resources (Hemalatha et al., 2022). Therefore, it is essential to find a reliable and continuous source of alternative material for fine aggregate that is eco-friendly and cheap. Copper slag is considered as one such material that has similar properties as river sand, such as silica (SiO₂) content.

Copper slag can also reduce the construction cost by saving in material cost. It can also reduce the heat of hydration, refine the pore structure and decrease the permeability of concrete. This paper investigates the effect of partial replacement of sand by copper slag on some of the mechanical properties of concrete, such as compressive strength, split tensile strength and flexural strength. It also compares the performance of copper slag with other fine aggregates, such as steel slag and tire waste. It aims to evaluate the feasibility and suitability of copper slag as a fine aggregate for concrete and to study its impact on the strength and durability of concrete.

1.1. Advantages of Using Copper Slag in Construction

- i. Reduces the construction cost due to saving in material cost. It reduces the heat of hydration. It refines the pore structure.
- ii. Reduces permeability.
- iii. Reduces the demand for primary natural resources.
- iv. Reduces the environmental impact due to quarrying and aggregate mining.
- v. Copper slag has similar properties as river sand and it contains silica (SiO₂) similar to sand.
- vi. Concrete is a most versatile construction material because it is designed to withstand the harsh environments. Engineers are continually pushing the limits to improve its performance with the help of innovative chemical admixtures and supplementary materials. These materials are majority by products from other processes. The use of these byproducts not only helps to utilize these waste materials but also enhances the properties of concrete in fresh and hydrated states. The usage of industrial byproducts especially industrial slags in making of concrete is an important study of worldwide interest.

2. Studies on the Utilization of Copper Slag in Construction Materials

2.1 Feasibility of Copper Slag in Land Reclamation (Lim and Chu, 2006)

The Lim and Chu (2006) conducted a study on the feasibility of using spent copper slag as fill material in land reclamation. The physical and geotechnical properties of the spent copper slag were first assessed by laboratory tests, including hydraulic conductivity and shear strength tests. The physical and geotechnical properties were compared with

those of conventional fill material such as sands. The potential Environmental Impacts Associated with the use of the spent copper slag for land reclamation were also evaluated by conducting laboratory tests including pH and Eh measurements, batch-leaching tests, Acid Neutralization Capacity Determination and Monitoring of long-term dissolution of the material. The spent copper slag was slightly alkaline, with pH 8.4 at a solid /water ratio of 1:1. The batch leaching test results showed that the concentrations of the regulated heavy metals leached from the material at pH 5.0. They were significantly lower than the maximum concentration for their toxicity limits referred by United States Toxicity Characteristic Leaching Procedure. They finally suggested that the spent copper slag was a good fill material and it can be used as a fill material for land reclamation.

2.2 Comprehensive Review of Copper Slag Characteristics (Alter, 2004)

Alter has conducted a recent comprehensive review on the characteristics and utilization of copper slag. It encourages Applications for this (properly) Several Important Pyro metallurgical by Product. However, the review does not include possible environmental effects from these slags. Literature reports were used to accumulate data describing the chemical composition and acid leaching of commercial copper slags from three countries. From these data, average values of chemical composition and their statistical confidence limits (95%) were calculated. The variability of the chemical analyses of three commercial slags produced over 19 or 20 months were statistically analyzed and shown to be small. He concluded that the concentrations of toxic heavy metals in the slags are low and the frequency distributions of the values are narrow and commercial copper slags have been determined to be non-hazardous.

2.3 Use of Copper Slag in Cement Clinker Production (Alpa and Devenci, 2008)

They studied the effect of copper slag in coarse aggregate type on mechanical properties of high-performance concrete. Tests were carried out to study the effect of the coarse aggregate type on the compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, fracture energy, characteristic length, and elastic modulus of concrete produced at different strength levels with 28-day target

compressive strengths of 30, 50 and 90 N/mm² respectively. Concrete was produced using crushed quartzite, Crushed granite, limestone, and marble coarse aggregate. The results showed that the strength, stiffness, and fracture energy of concrete for a given water/cement ratio (W/C) depend on the type of aggregate, especially for high-strength concrete. It was suggested that high-strength concrete with lower brittleness can be made by selecting high-strength aggregate with low brittleness.

Alpa and Devenci (2008) reported the potential use of flotation waste of a copper slag as an iron source in the production of Portland cement clinker. The FWCS appears a suitable raw material as iron source containing greater than 59% Fe₂O₃ mainly in the form of hematite (Fe₂SiO₄) and magnetite (Fe₃O₄). The clinker products obtained using the FWCS from the industrial scale trial operations over a four month period were characterized for the conformity of its chemical composition. The physico-mechanical performance of the resultant cement products was evaluated. The data collected for the clinker products (produced using an iron ore is currently used as cement raw material. It was also included for comparison.

The results have shown that the chemical compositions of all the clinker products including those of FWCS are typical of a Portland cement clinker. The mechanical performance of the standard mortars prepared from the FWCS clinkers was found to be similar to those of the iron ore clinkers with the desired specifications for the industrial cements. Furthermore, the leachability tests have revealed that the mortar samples obtained from the FWCS clinkers present no environmental problems while the FWCS could act as the potential source of heavy metal contamination. These findings suggest that flotation wastes of copper slag (EWCS) can be readily utilized as cement raw material due to its availability in large quantities at low cost. This has got significant benefits management/environmental practices for waste of the FWCS, reduced production and processing costs for cement raw materials.

Mostafa Khanradi and Ali Behnood (2009) presented the results of a study undertaken to investigate the feasibility of using copper slag as coarse aggregates in high-strength concrete. The effects of replacing limestone coarse aggregate by

copper slag coarse aggregate on the compressive strength, splitting tensile strength and rebound hammer values of high-strength concretes are evaluated in this work. Concrete mixtures containing different levels of silica fume were prepared with water to cementitious materials ratios of 0.40, 0.35 and 0.30. The percentages of the cement replacements by silica fume were 0%, 6% and 10%. The use of copper slag aggregate compared to limestone aggregate resulted in a 28-day compressive strength increase of about 10-5% and a splitting tensile strength increase of 10-18%. It can be concluded from the results of this study that using copper slag as coarse aggregate in high-strength concrete is technically possible and useful.

Najimi et al., (2011) investigated the performance of copper slag contained concrete in sulphate solution. In this regard, an experimental study including expansion measurements, compressive strength degradation and micro structural analysis were conducted in sulphate solution on concretes. This was made by replacing 0%, 5%, 10% and 15% of cement with copper slag waste. The results of this study emphasized the effectiveness of copper slag replacement in improving the concrete resistance against sulphate attack.

Rathan Raj et al., (2007) suggested that High-Reactivity Metakaolin and Alumina Red Mud in dry densified form can be used for the partial replacement of cement and super plasticizer. Flat shaped HRM and ARM in small percentage improved the mechanical and durability characteristics of concrete. Super plasticizer improved the workability of concrete and made possible to get sufficient workable concrete of lower water binder ratio. They reported that, out of the various percentages of HRM and ARM as admixtures, the concrete with 8% replacement of cement with admixtures gives better results. Based upon the experimental investigation carried out, the following conclusions were drawn.

- i. Concrete with 8% replacement of HRM and ARM behaved better than the concrete without any admixtures.
- ii. Addition of HRM and ARM replaced cement in concrete improved the corrosion resistance of the concrete without any reduction in compressive strength.

Matsuda et al (2005) investigated the applications of Granulated Blast Furnace Slag to reduce seismic earth pressure. The granulated Blast Furnace shows a similar particle formation as a natural sand and also low weight, high shear strength, well permeability and especially a latent hydraulic property by which GBF is similar to dense rock. In this study, the model wall tests were carried out on GBFS, in which the resultant earth pressure, a wall friction and the earth pressure distribution at the wall surface were measured, and the test results were compared with those of Toyoura standard sand. It was clarified that the resultant earth pressure obtained by using GBFS was smaller than Toyoura sand, especially in the active-earth pressure. Al-Jabri et al (2011) investigated the "effect of using copper slag as a fine aggregate" on the properties of cement mortars and concrete. Various mortar and concrete mixtures were prepared with different proportions of copper slag ranging from 0% (for the control mixture) to 100%. The fine aggregates refinement. Cement mortar mixtures were evaluated for compressive strength, whereas concrete mixtures were evaluated for workability, density, compressive strength, tensile strength, flexural strength and durability. The results obtained for cement mortars revealed that all mixtures with different copper slag proportions yielded comparable or higher compressive strength than that of the control mixture. The results demonstrated that surface water absorption decreased as copper slag content increases up to 50% replacement. Beyond that, the absorption rate increased rapidly and the percentage volume of the permeable voids was comparable to the control mixture. Therefore, it was recommended that up to 40-50% (by weight of sand) of copper slag can be used as a replacement for fine aggregates in order to obtain a concrete with good strength and durability requirements. Mostafa Khanzadi and AlBehnood (2009) presented the results of a study undertaken to investigate the feasibility of using copper slag as coarse aggregates in high-strength concrete. The percentages of the cement replacements by silica fume were 0%, 6% and 10%. The use of copper slag aggregate compared to limestone aggregate resulted in a 28-day compressive strength increase of about 10-15% and a splitting tensile strength increase of 10-18%. It can be concluded from the results of this study that

using copper slag as coarse aggregate in high-strength concrete is technically possible and useful. Zerdi conducted an "Experimental Investigation on properties of Concrete by Replacement Copper Slag for Fine Aggregate". The fine aggregates were replaced with percentages 0% (for the control mix), 20%, 40%, and 60% of Copper Slag by weight. Tests were performed for properties of fresh concrete and Hardened Concrete. Compressive strength was determined at 3, 7, 14 and 28 days. Improvement in the strength properties of plain concrete by the inclusion of up to 40% Copper slag as replacement of fine aggregate was observed as 25.58 N/mm² at 28 days for M20 concrete. Madhavi, Paven Kumar & Jothilingam studied on "Effect of Copper Slag on the Mechanical Strengths of Concrete, experimental investigations are carried out replacing the sand with copper slag in proportions of 10%, 20%, 30%, 40%, 50%, 60% and 100% keeping all other ingredients constant. It was seen that the optimum content of copper slag is 40% beyond which the strength starts.

3. Materials and Methodology

1510

- i. Cement-Ordinary Portland cement of 53 grade conforming to Indian Standard IS 12269-1987 was used throughout the experimental program.
- ii. Fine aggregate (Natural River Fine Aggregate): Locally available river sand having density of 1600 kg/m³ and fineness Modulus (FM) of 2.45 is used. The specific gravity was found to be 2.70 as per IS 383:1970.
- iii. Copper slag is an irregular, black, glassy and granular in nature and its properties are similar to the river sand. In this project, Copper slag used is brought from Industry in India. Every ton of copper will generate approximately 2.2-3 tons of copper slag. The Industry produces 400,000/year of copper and during the process around 800,000t of copper slag is generated in a year. The chemical traces such as copper, sulphate and alumina in a presenting the slag are not harmful.
- iv. Coarse Aggregate: -
- v. Crushed hard basalt chips of maximum size 20 mm were used in the concrete mixes. The bulk density of aggregate was 1545 kg/m³ and specific gravity was found to be 2.74
- vi. Water: -Potable water conforming to IS 456-

2011 was used for casting and curing.

3.1. Material Preparation: -

3.1.1. Cement

The ordinary Portland cement (OPC) of 53 grade having specific gravity of 3.15 was decided to use in this study. It was tested for its physical properties in accordance with Indian standard specification.

3.1.2. Fine Aggregate

The sand particles should be free from any clay or inorganic materials and found to be hard and durable.

3.1.3. Coarse Aggregate

Coarse aggregates of 10 mm and 20 mm size is used for the study and natural and of river bed disused confirming to grading of IS 383 were procured from local river in Maharashtra.

Fig 2. Preparation of Sample for Cube molds with Copper Slag

3.1.4. Water

Water gives strength to cement and workability to the concrete. Drinking water is used for casting and curing of the concrete blocks.

3.1.5. Copper Slag

Copper slag is an irregular, black, glassy and granular in nature and its properties are similar to the river sand. In this project, Copper slag used is brought from Industry in India. Every ton of copper will generate approximately 2.2-3 tons of copper slag. The Industry produces 400,000/year of copper and during the process around 800,000t of copper slag is generated in a year. The chemical traces such

as copper, sulphate and alumina presenting the slag are not harmful.

4. Conclusion

- i. The workability of concrete increased with the increase in copper slag content offine aggregate replacements at same water-cement ratio is expected.
- ii. The replacement offine aggregate using copper slag in concrete increases the density of concrete, compressive strength, flexural strength, tensile strength is expected.
- iii. Replacement of copper slag in both fine aggregate

esandcementreplacementreducesthecost ofmaking concrete is expected. In this report experimental results are presented to evaluate the feasibility of partial replacement of fine aggregate by using copper slag in concrete. Such as 0%, 15%, 30%, 45%,60% By using M20 grade ofconcrete. In this study compressive test, splittensile test & flexural strength test were done on concrete with varying percentages refinement offline aggregate by using copper slag in concrete.

- iv. The experimentstudyshown the resultofcompressivestrengthofconcrete specimenshigher value at 45% replacement offline aggregate using copper slag. The split tensile strength ofhardened concrete increases marginally till 45% replacement of sand by copper slag
- v. It is observed that up to 45% replacement ofnatural sand by copper slag, the flexural strength of concrete is increased. So it is recommended that 45% offline aggregate can be replaced by copper slag. Use of copper slag as partial replacement of FA can reduces th ecostof construction for 45% replacement of copper slag, saving in cost is 11%. The aim of project top romoteusability of copper slag to substitute natural fine aggregate in building construction, road construction in cement concrete, concrete beam, column, slab and concrete wall in canal.

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